

Supplementary information - Rise and diversification of chondrichthyans in the Paleozoic

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Figure S1: Relative genus abundance of chondrichthyans for each stage of the Paleozoic. Silurian in yellow, Devonian in turquoise, Carboniferous in blue and Permian in red.

Figure S2: Changes in total chondrichthyan sample coverage (quantified via Good's u estimator) through the Paleozoic.

Figure S3: Chondrichthyan local richness (alpha diversity) in the Paleozoic after removing the three highest collections (Armagh, Alton, Illinois).

Figure S4: Coverage-based (A, B) and sample-size-based (C, D) rarefaction (solid line) and extrapolation (dotted line) curves for all investigated intervals of the Paleozoic. A, C, Silurian (lightgreen) and Devonian (yellow). B, D, Carboniferous (blue) and Permian (red). Extrapolated lines (dotted) represent the Chao1 extrapolator (see Hsieh *et al.* 2016). Ae, Aeronian; Ar, Artinskian; As, Asselian; Ba, Bashkirian; Ca, Capitanian; Cha, Changhsingian; Ei, Eifelian; Em, Emsian; Fam, Fammenian; Fra, Frasnian; Gi, Givetian; Gz, Gzhelian; Ho, Homeric; Ka, Kasimovian; Ku, Kungurian; Lo, Lochkovian; Mo, Moscovian; Pr, Pridoli; Pra, Pragian; Rh, Rhuddanian; Ro, Roadian; Sa, Sakmarian; Se, Serpukhovian; Sh, Sheinwoodian; Te, Telychian; To, Tournaisian; Vi, Visean Wu, Wuchiapingian.

Table S1: Metrics of diversity dynamics through time for Paleozoic chondrichthyans. **max**, maximum age. **min**, minimum age. **mid**, midpoint. **tSing**, number of stratigraphic singleton taxa. **tOri**, number of originating taxa. **tExt**, number of taxa getting extinct. **divSIB**, sampled-in-bin diversity. **divRT**, range-through diversity. **ext2f3**, second-for-third extinction rates (based on Alroy 2015). **ori2f3**, second-for-third origination rates (based on Alroy 2015).

stage	max	min	mid	tSing	tOri	tExt	divSIB	divRT	ext2f3	ori2f3
Darriwilian	467.3	458.4	462.85	1	0	NA	1	1	NA	NA
Sandbian	458.4	453	455.7	3	0	0	3	3	NA	NA
Katian	453	445.2	449.1	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA
Hirnantian	445.2	443.8	444.5	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA
Rhuddanian	443.8	440.8	442.3	0	3	0	3	3	NA	NA
Aeronian	440.8	438.5	439.65	1	4	0	8	8	0	0.847298
Telychian	438.5	433.4	435.95	8	2	1	17	17	0.154151	0.287682
Sheinwoodian	433.4	430.5	431.95	2	3	4	13	13	0.693147	0.559616
Homerian	430.5	427.4	428.95	0	2	3	9	9	0.847298	0.510826
Gorstian	427.4	425.6	426.5	0	10	0	15	16	0.510826	1.466337
Ludfordian	425.6	423	424.3	1	2	1	16	19	0.080043	0.167054
Pridoli	423	419.2	421.1	5	10	4	28	32	0.367725	0.641854
Lochkovian	419.2	410.8	415	38	25	8	84	86	0.546544	1.131402
Pragian	410.8	407.6	409.2	3	5	8	40	48	0.11441	0
Emsian	407.6	393.3	400.45	14	13	16	60	64	0.693147	0.485508
Eifelian	393.3	387.7	390.5	3	7	11	38	44	0.336472	0.213574
Givetian	387.7	382.7	385.2	9	6	11	42	45	0.538997	0.223144
Frasnian	382.7	372.2	377.45	12	10	8	43	47	0.356675	0.613104
Famennian	372.2	358.9	365.55	13	13	16	50	53	1.056053	0.741937
Tournaisian	358.9	346.7	352.8	8	50	4	81	82	0.271934	1.481605
Visean	346.7	330.9	338.8	27	12	4	105	109	0.077558	0.154151
Serpukhovian	330.9	323.2	327.05	15	4	26	89	97	0.470004	0.045462
Bashkirian	323.2	315.2	319.2	3	16	4	65	75	0.067441	0.333144
Moscovian	315.2	307	311.1	28	4	6	93	100	0.093526	0.019418
Kasimovian	307	303.7	305.35	2	2	1	60	70	-0.01739	0.016529
Gzhelian	303.7	298.9	301.3	6	2	43	70	75	1.645156	0.074108
Asselian	298.9	293.52	296.21	0	9	3	25	35	0.143101	0.526093
Sakmarian	293.52	290.1	291.81	1	4	0	28	37	0	0.117783
Artinskian	290.1	283.5	286.8	1	3	5	33	40	0.167054	0.167054
Kungurian	283.5	272.95	278.225	2	2	17	32	38	0.955511	0.09531
Roadian	272.95	268.8	270.875	3	4	3	22	26	0.287682	0.559616
Wordian	268.8	265.1	266.95	0	2	1	16	22	0	0
Capitanian	265.1	259.1	262.1	0	0	8	15	21	0.628609	-0.11778
Wuchiapingian	259.1	254.14	256.62	0	4	3	17	17	NA	0.693147
Changhsingian	254.14	251.902	253.021	1	NA	14	15	15	NA	NA

Figure S5: Chondrichthyan subsampled genus diversity with Holocephali/Euchondrocephali excluded. A and C, coverage-standardized diversity at different quorum levels. B and D, squares diversity. A and B, total group Holocephali as per most recent phylogenies. C and D, Euchondrocephali sensu Ginter *et al.* 2010.

Figure S6: Subsampled and raw richness estimates of Chondrichthyan subclasses, based on the systematics from Ginter *et al.* 2010. A, squares diversity. B, raw sampled-in-bin richness.

Figure S7: Raw richness stacked area plot of the two chondrichthyan subclasses, Elasmobranchii and Holocephali.

Figure S8: Local richness (alpha diversity) from the Ordovician to the Permian divided into freshwater and marine occurrences. Local richness is the number of genera per collection/fossil locality.

Figure S9: Local richness (alpha diversity) divided into benthic assemblage zones (BA) from the Ordovician to the Permian. Local richness is the number of genera per collection/ fossil locality.

Figure S10: Subsampled and raw richness estimates of chondrichthyans divided by modern continents. A, squares diversity. B, raw sampled-in-bin richness.

Figure S11. Time series of global and regional level paleogeographic spreads. MST, minimum spanning tree. GCD, great-circle distance. PD, pairwise distance.